

Meaningful Learning through Gamification in Botanical Studies

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Abstract

Despite the importance of botany, it is not receiving the necessary attention to strengthen student learning. To contribute to a solution to this problem, the objective was to determine the effect of gamification on the meaningful learning of botany among students at a higher technical institution in Cañete, Peru. To achieve this objective, a quantitative method was used, adopting a quasi-experimental design with a sample of 60 students divided into two groups of 30. To measure the meaningful learning variable, a knowledge test was used, validated by 8 experts and with a Cronbach's alpha reliability of 0.825. In addition, 10 botany learning sessions were conducted using gamified sessions that included Wordwall and Blooket tools. The results derived from the Mann-Whitney U analysis with $\text{Sig.} < 0.05$ and $z = 2.811$, with a Cohen's d value = 9.01939 reflect improvements in meaningful learning more pronounced in the experimental group, so it is stated that gamification presents positive and significant effects of gamification on the meaningful learning of botany. Therefore, it is concluded that the implementation of gamification is a key resource to strengthen the learning of botany.

Keywords: meaningful learning, botany, strategy, gamification, motivation

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Problematic Reality

Despite the importance of botany in the contemporary world, Husamah et al. [1], considered that students do not show enough interest for a deeper learning of botany, which has been called plant blindness, and have pointed out a series of factors such as the deficiency of educational resources and the little commitment on the part of students as limitations of learning. In the same problematic line, Anggarani et al. [2], highlighted their concern for the low level of botanical literacy of students, which is manifested in a poor capacity for understanding plants and their topics, a situation that can be aggravated by decreasing the interest of students and the reduction of botany teachers.

In this scenario, Gutiérrez et al. [3], highlighted that the inclusion of experiential methodologies is essential to captivate students and achieve the expected immersion and learning, which could ultimately contribute to education for sustainable development. Likewise, Marwah and Wally [4], discussed the importance of applying innovative learning media to make students' learning in botany more exciting and understandable. In this sense, Pashina and Arbuzova [5], highlighted that the use of emerging digital technologies by teachers represents viable, effective, and innovative alternatives to contribute to the learning of botany in higher education students.

In this context, the main objective for teachers is to achieve greater motivation and deeper learning in botany. Therefore, the present study, motivated by students' learning deficiencies and lack of interest, seeks to inspire educational and recreational strategies such as gamification to enhance teaching and learning.

This research is justified from a theoretical perspective because there is limited literature that addresses the benefits of gamification in deep learning of botany. Although there are investigations such as those carried out by Mendoza et al. [6], Plúas and Joseph [7] and Mendieta et al. [8], which have examined the benefits of gamification in learning botany, biology and history, a conspicuous gap was evident in the context of botany learning, which limits the opportunity for different and innovative learning that favors the construction of complex knowledge in taxonomy, plant physiology and other topics of botany. Furthermore, research on these topics tends to study gamification and meaningful learning separately, so due importance has not been given to the synergistic study of gamification not only to motivate the student, but also to achieve deeper learning as postulated by Ausubel's theory. For this reason, the present study addressed a solid conceptual framework based on Ausubel's theory of meaningful learning to validate that the incorporation of gamification strategies contributes to improving deep learning in botany.

This research was conducted to evaluate the effect of gamification on deep learning in botany among students at a technical college in Cañete, Peru. The findings are expected to serve as a solid foundation for the development of gamified sessions for botany and related courses in higher technical education.

B. Literature Review

Conceptualization of gamification

According to Kirchner et al. [9], gamification refers to an innovative and technological initiative that takes advantage of the integration of playful resources to promote more interesting or fun learning, in order to increase the level of motivation and stimulate more relevant learning. Similarly, from the perspective of Swanepoel [10], gamification refers to the pedagogical strategy that consists of the incorporation of playful elements for learning contexts with the idea of changing the traditional learning experience to give way to a fun, enjoyable experience that, by using the elements and components of games, takes advantage of playful activation through skills, which increases student participation. Likewise, for Vital [11], it is specified that gamification is a technique that includes gamification strategies, which consists of adopting a game approach to learning situations, through the activation of the brain, generating a fun experience in learning, which is useful to promote student motivation and participation.

Relevant theories of gamification

Whitton and Moseley developed the theory of gamification-mediated learning, which explains that the implementation of this strategy works as a driver or catalyst for motivation and learning. This means that gamification [12]. Similarly, there is Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi's flow theory, which details that there is a flow that reflects an optimal state in which it resembles an

optimal experience due to the intervention of gamification [13]. Likewise, another theory that supports gamification is the Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning, which refers to those principles with which strategies are designed to ensure that students acquire the desired learning while avoiding distractions or behaviors that do not favor learning [14].

Dimensions of gamification

Regarding the dimensions of gamification, the following are distinguished: mechanics, dynamics and components. Regarding the mechanical dimension, which are those conditions of the gamified game that offers players a game scenario in which actions, behaviors and mechanisms of the game are located that involve the student player in learning mediated by the game, the dynamic dimension refers to the way in which the dynamics are carried out, that is, the way in which the gamification process is executed, in which the teacher uses dynamics to motivate the student both in their participation and their active learning and the components dimension, refers to the resources and tools that are available and used to design a gamified activity, which will be designed or structured from the inclusion of elements such as music, history, images and others that provide it with an attractive appearance so that the student gets hooked on the activity [15].

Meaningful learning

From the perspective of David Ausubel, meaningful learning refers to the process in which new knowledge is integrated with pre-existing knowledge, from which knowledge is produced or learning is generated [16]. In addition, it is described as a strategy that, when implemented, has the purpose of the student acquiring knowledge based on previous experiences, and the knowledge acquired is based on the understanding of meanings, which facilitates the application of these in new situations or contexts [17]. Likewise, meaningful learning is considered an educational theory and is defined as the process in which the student manages to acquire knowledge that is built on the basis of previous information and the connection that is established by giving it meanings, so that learning is retained more easily, can be remembered and applied with greater transfer of knowledge. In addition, for meaningful learning to develop properly, it must include five aspects: a) learning must be an active process, the activities that are developed must prioritize the interaction and management of information; b) learning involves the construction of knowledge from the understanding and reflection of meanings; c) this type of learning has an intention, therefore its purpose must be the acquisition or achievement of learning; d) learning must be authentic, this refers to the fact that it should not be learned for the sake of learning, but rather to take advantage of what was learned to put such knowledge into practice in real situations; e) learning must be cooperative, so that students can share ideas and work together reinforcing their knowledge [18].

Similarly, meaningful learning is characterized by the following principles: a) connection with prior knowledge, since in order to learn, it is necessary to establish a link between what is known and what is acquired, because in order to learn something new, there must be prior information, in this way learning will be deeper; b) active participation, this presupposes that the student who participates will not be a mere receiver of knowledge, but that his interaction will favor his learning; c) contextualization, since in order to verify that the knowledge was acquired, the student must be able to contextualize the learning; d) social interaction, since learning involves asking questions, inquiring, and other activities that require interaction with the teacher and other students [19].

Other characteristics that have been specified for meaningful learning include: a) the potential meaning of knowledge, this means that, to achieve this type of learning, the student must perceive that what he or she will learn will be very relevant, this will stimulate its acquisition since he or she will be able to connect or link what he or she already knows with what is new; b) psychological meaning, refers to the integration of knowledge, emphasizing the internalization of knowledge, that is, making new information one's own; c) sharing meanings, which leads to sharing information that enriches learning since not all people think the same way, and they may have different views and also important contributions [20].

Theories linked to meaningful learning

Ausubel's theory of meaningful learning raises the idea of learning based on what is defined as "cognitive structure", which reflects the mental space and singularity where concepts are processed or organized and meaningful learning entails the improvement of the structure, this means that learning is a synergy of previous schemes or previous knowledge with current information [16]. Jerome Bruner's constructivist theory raised how people think and learn, which he called two modalities of complementary and irreducible cognitive functioning, from which they explain the way of constructing reality, which is not the same in each person, since each person will have a perspective of understanding reality [21]. The theory of conceptual maps developed by Novak [22], raised a reflection on how to achieve learning under constructivist guidelines of learning, focusing on the way in which students prioritize the new information obtained and manage to establish a cognitive bridge between what the student already has as prior knowledge and what he is acquiring as part of his learning process. In other words, the mind map

seeks to have the student demonstrate his knowledge while taking advantage of the synthesis of information that allows verifying that students reach an understanding of the topics.

Furthermore, it highlights Bloom's taxonomy as a theory that underpins meaningful learning based on educational objectives that are organized hierarchically and coincide with the level of cognitive skills necessary for carrying out tasks and learning that range from the most basic to the advanced notions. According to this model, six skills are required which, when integrated with Ausubel's theory, the skills of remembering and understanding would correspond to previous knowledge, the skills of understanding and applying correspond to the assimilation dimension, and the skills of applying, analyzing, evaluating, and creating correspond to the construction of new knowledge dimension [23].

Dimensions of meaningful learning

To evaluate meaningful learning, the following dimensions were adopted: The dimension, prior knowledge refers to the set of knowledge, experiences and attitudes that a student already has prior to the new learning process. This dimension includes the relevance of the prior knowledge that the student brings with him, as well as the ability to relate this knowledge to new concepts and real situations, the assimilation dimension that represents the ability to understand in greater depth the information of a particular topic or content, in addition, it implies the skill to express what has been acquired in one's own words, as well as knowing how to use them for different contexts and the knowledge construction component consists of information, which implies a greater skill to link concepts of the subject in practical circumstances [24].

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Method

The approach adopted in the present research was quantitative. According to Menacho et al. [25], these studies are distinguished because to test a hypothesis, it requires the use of techniques and methods to collect information and evaluate it through statistical procedures. This approach belongs to the positivist paradigm, described by Romero et al. [26], as the way to reach knowledge through the scientific method, which is useful for understanding, explaining, controlling and predicting the phenomena under study.

The type of study is classified as applied. According to Moreno et al. [27], these studies refer to the application of knowledge with the intention of changing, modifying or improving a situation that has been considered deficient. In addition, the design corresponding to the study is quasi-experimental with the presence of two groups: control and experimental. From the perspective of Aguirre [28], these studies are characterized because an intervention is carried out in the experimental group and is compared with the control group to evaluate the effectiveness of the intervention.

B. Participants

The study population consisted of 113 students from a technical college, and the sample consisted of 60 students, of which 30 were part of the control group and 30 were part of the experimental group. Regarding the inclusion criteria, students from the botany course at the technical college who decided to participate in the study and signed their consent were included. Students who had missed the course, or students with medical conditions or other conditions that prevented them from participating in the study were also excluded.

C. Research techniques

To obtain information, Huairé et al. [29] specified that techniques refer to methods for obtaining information. In addition, Ortiz et al. [30] indicated that due to the characteristics of the study and quasi-experimental objectives, the knowledge test allows obtaining information about the learning of botany. To evaluate significant learning, a pre-test and post-test botany knowledge test was used. This instrument is made up of 16 questions arranged in three dimensions: prior knowledge (6 questions); assimilation (4 questions); and, knowledge construction (6 questions), which is rated according to a rubric that has an ordinal scale: excellent (5); outstanding (4); good (3); basic (2); incipient (1).

Table I
Questions by achievement indicator

Previous knowledge	Assimilation	Knowledge construction	Achievement indicators
1, 2	10	15	Identify, describe and analyze the morphology of the plant, according to the type of species.
3, 4	8, 9	11, 12, 13, 14	Recognize, describe and analyze the physiological characteristics of the plant, according to the species.
5			It identifies and describes the biochemical, cellular, and molecular bases that govern plant functioning, taking into account the interaction between endogenous and environmental factors.
6	7	16	Recognize and exemplify the variety of species, taking into account the morphology of the plant. Analyzes the preparation of herbariums (corn, potato, sweet potato, citrus, avocado, blueberries, pecan, vegetables) according to taxonomic classification.

The botany knowledge test, which assesses meaningful learning, was examined by a panel of experts as part of the validation process. A pilot test was also conducted to evaluate the instrument's reliability, yielding a reliability of 0.825, classifying the test as adequate.

D. Procedure

To implement gamification, 10 botany learning sessions were prepared, each lasting 1.5 hours. Two technological tools were used: Wordwall for the gamified activities and Blooket for the end-of-session assessments. Each learning session was divided into three phases: the first, 15 minutes long, was used to introduce the topic and explain the methodology of the gamified session. The second phase was the development phase, which consisted of implementing Wordwall according to the topic or learning session. The final phase was the closing phase, during which reflection and knowledge assessments were conducted using the Blooket tool.

Table II
Gamified sessions of the botany subject

Session	Botany Theme	Gamified activity	Objective	Evaluation	Duration
1	Classification and division		Learn about the main divisions and classifications of plants.		
2	Plant cell		Understanding the structure of plant cells.		
3	Plant tissue		Learn about plant tissue.		
4	Root system		Learn about the root system.		1 ½ hours
5	The stem	Wordwall	Understanding the function of the stem.	Blooket	per session
6	The leaf		Learn about the classification of leaves.		
7	The flower		Understanding the characteristics of flowers.		
8	The fruit		Understanding how fruits work.		
9	Photosynthesis		Understand the meaning of photosynthesis.		
10	Herbariums		Understanding herbariums.		

E. Information analysis

To analyze the information, we used Excel and SPSS statistical software version 31, and two complementary analyses were performed: The first was a descriptive analysis using central tendency measures to obtain information about differences in means and other indicators. The second analysis was inferential, used to test statistical hypotheses. To this end, the Shapiro Wilk normality test was first performed, reporting that the samples as a whole did not have a normal distribution. Therefore, to test the hypotheses, the Wilcoxon test for paired samples (intragroup) and the Mann-Whitney U test for independent samples (intergroup) were used [31].

III.RESULTS

A. Descriptive results

Based on the report in Table III, which shows the measures of central tendency used to compare the pretest and posttest evaluations for each group, it can be seen that there are no significant differences in the pretest, so it can be assumed that both the experimental and control groups are in almost the same conditions. On the contrary, according to the post-test report, more marked differences are observed, reflecting an increase in scores or averages, which implies that gamification used in botany learning sessions has had better results than traditional botany classes without any intervention.

Table III
Measures of central tendency

Groups	Average	Confidence interval 95%	Median	Variance	Standard deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Pretest_GC	47.60	[42.65-52.55]	40.00	175.903	13.263	29	73
Pretest_GE	50.57	[45.61-55.52]	54.50	176.185	13.273	34	71
Post_test_GC	56.20	[52.96-59.44]	58.00	75.269	8.676	36	74
Post_test_GE	62.47	[58.98-65.96]	65.50	87.430	9.350	43	74

Nota. GC = Control group; GE = Experimental group; IC = Confidence index al 95.0%

B. Normality test

The Shapiro Wilk normality test shows that all significance levels were less than 0.05 except for the post-test of the control group. Therefore, it can be seen that the samples do not have a normal distribution, meaning that non-parametric tests are appropriate for both intragroup and intergroup analysis. This means that Wilcoxon tests are applied for paired samples (intragroup) and the Mann-Whitney U test for independent samples (intergroup).

Table IV
Normality test Shapiro Wilk

	Statistician	gl	Sig.
Pretest_GC	.856	30	<.001
Pretest_GE	.865	30	.001
Post_test_GC	.978	30	.756
Post_test_GE	.894	30	.006

C. Hypothesis testing

Intergroup test for the general hypothesis

Ha: Gamification improves meaningful learning of botany in students of Higher Technological Education, Cañete - 2024.

Ho: Gamification does not improve meaningful learning of botany in students of technological higher education, Cañete - 2024.

In Table V, in coherence with the intergroup report, carried out using the Mann-Whitney U test because it is a non-parametric test according to the normality of the data and because it corresponds to independent samples, a significance of Sig. = 0.005 is shown, being less than 0.05, so it can be stated that there is evidence to accept the alternative hypothesis, verifying that the implementation of gamification contributes to improving the meaningful learning of botany.

Table V
Intergroup test for meaningful learning

	Pretest	Post-test
U de Mann-Whitney	510.000	640.000
W de Wilcoxon	975.000	1105.000
Z	.889	2.811
Sig. asintótica (bilateral test)	.374	.005

Table VI, consistent with the report, shows that the standardized value of Cohen's d was 9.01939, representing a high value, meaning that the impact of gamification is high, confirming the positive effect on learning botany.

Table VI

Effect size

			Confidence interval at 95%	
			Lower	Superior
	Standardizer ^a	Point estimation		
Intervention	d de Cohen	9.01939	-1.214	-.170
	Correction de Hedges	9.13815	-1.198	-.168
	Delta de Glass	9.35039	-1.199	-.131

Intragroup test for the general hypothesis

Ho: There is no difference in the medians of the groups

Ha: There are differences in the medians of the groups

As can be seen in Table VII in the intragroup report, the significance in both cases is less than 0.05, so it can be inferred that, in both cases, there are significant differences. It can be seen that for the control group there are significant differences in the medians, as there are for the experimental group. However, as demonstrated previously, the effect was more positive for the experimental group that received the gamification intervention.

Table VII

Intragroup reporting for both groups

	PretestGC – PosttestGC	PretestGE – PosttestGE
Z	-3.810 ^b	-4.784 ^b
Sig. asin. (bilateral)	<.001	<.001

IV. DISCUSSION

According to the results produced by the statistical analysis, the hypotheses proposed in the research have been verified. Based on this and in line with the overall objective, it was found that the implementation of gamification in students improves meaningful learning in botany. This result is supported by the nonparametric analysis for two independent samples using the Mann-Whitney U test, which yielded statistical reports of a difference in means that was significant according to Sig. = 0.005 < 0.05 with $z = 2.811 > 1.96$, which favored the experimental group over the control group, showing that the group that received gamification significantly improved their learning of botany. On the other hand, Cohen's d effect size was 9.01939, which verified a positive effect in the use of gamification. To achieve this result, Wordwall and Blooket tools were used, which facilitated the design of gamified activities, which students accessed through their mobile devices. The application of these tools became an ally for the teacher, as the activities implemented were carried out in real time with direct feedback and with the participation of all students belonging to the experimental group through which botany was taught.

In support of these results, the research by Manivel et al. [32] agrees, reporting significant differences in academic performance that favor the experimental group among university students after applying gamification. This was verified using the T-student test, which obtained a significance of less than 0.05, demonstrating that gamification significantly increases

academic performance. To achieve these results, the researchers incorporated gamification resources using the Genially platform, which changed the students' learning experiences through interactive activities that included game mechanisms to achieve greater learning. After these gamified experiences, students have shown greater interest in the subject, which is considered complicated, and have also reported greater ease in understanding the topics covered, which has promoted deeper learning.

Similarly, the results are consistent with the findings of Robles et al. [33], who verified the effect of using Quizizz on learning. Furthermore, according to the university students' perceptions, gamified classes using Quizizz encourage a proactive attitude, with students showing greater interest and participation in both learning and assessment activities. According to these findings, gamified activities with Quizizz are interactive and allow for direct feedback, which enables students to immediately recognize their successes and mistakes. Furthermore, this research was supported by the theory of connectivism developed by Downes and Siemens, which states that student learning is related to the interaction of networks through technological means.

The findings obtained are relevant and consistent with those reported by Plúas and Joseph [7], who found that the application of gamification as a teaching strategy contributes beneficially to increasing learning levels in the field of biology. They also revealed that, due to its playful nature, gamification led to students acquiring greater interest and demonstrating additional commitment, which has generated optimal learning. According to these findings, gamification increases students' interest in biology, which in turn increases their commitment. When participating in gamified teaching, learning is perceived as enjoyable, and as if they were competing with each other, students strive to achieve better results than their peers, since the teaching is public and everyone participates.

The results are also consistent with the study reported by Qub'a et al [34], whose research has shown that gamification used as a teaching method promotes student learning in the area of English. Furthermore, according to the descriptive information, 75.0% of students have experienced high levels of participation, which has led to greater engagement, increasing their retention and comprehension skills in the English language. According to these researchers, gamified sessions are perceived by students as fun, playful activities, and based on competition, scoring, and other elements and components of gamification, students feel more engaged, which contributes positively to increasing motivation and, therefore, learning in the subject described.

In this regard, Castellano et al [35] have pointed out that the use of tools designed for gamification contributes to increasing motivation and participation in learning, as well as strengthening learning and enabling students to enjoy learning experiences. Furthermore, these researchers have pointed out that gamification is a learning experience that involves all students and therefore feedback is spontaneous, direct, and allows the teacher to ask questions so that students can think properly, generating deeper learning.

V. CONCLUSIONS

It was concluded that the application of gamification in students of Higher Technological Education, Cañete – 2024 contributes significantly to improving meaningful learning in the botany course, based on the statistical report of the post-test with median differences that favor the EG over the CG, which are significant according to Sig. = 0.005 < 0.05 and with a positive effect reported in Cohen's $d = 9.01939$.

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